

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21037380>

The perceptions of CIFS students on increasing hours dedicated to discussing emotional intelligence in existing modules at WIUT

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ABSTRACT

Emotional Intelligence can influence many parts of our lives, from academic grades to job performance and thus, is vital in school, university and the workplace. This study investigates CIFS students' perceptions at Westminster International University in Tashkent (WIUT) regarding the allocation of greater seminar time to EI development within existing modules. This report explores recent studies and articles to understand the impacts of Emotional Intelligence on well-being and academic and work performance. For the primary research component, a quantitative cross-sectional research design was employed, with data collected through a 13-item questionnaire comprising multiple-choice, ranking, and open-ended questions. Participants were recruited through convenience sampling via institutional Telegram channels, yielding a total of 68 Level 3 CIFS students. The data revealed positive responses from participants, highlighting their recognition of the importance of Emotional Intelligence in enhancing academic performance, students' well-being, and preparation for the workplace. Another finding is that although students recognized the importance of Emotional Intelligence in academic success, achieving better career outcomes and well-being, some of them were still unsure about its application in academic settings. From these findings, recommendations are proposed for increasing the hours dedicated to Emotional Intelligence within the WIUT curriculum, with the aim of enhancing students' awareness of the significance of EI in academic and professional settings.

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence, academic performance, students' well-being, career success, stress management, university curriculum*

INTRODUCTION

Background information

Quality education is a common goal all over the world, which is also indicated in the SDGs of the UN. According to the United Nations (2020), it is important to provide everyone with adequate education due to its essential role in achieving other SDGs, including gender equality and eliminating poverty. Additionally, enhancing education results in technological innovations and economic advances (Runde, Bandura and McLean, 2023). While academic knowledge remains central to quality education, attention is increasingly being directed toward emotional and social competencies such as Emotional Intelligence (EI). Indeed, developing Emotional Intelligence is equally essential, as it has a direct correlation with academic and professional success.

Specific information

IQ has traditionally been used to assess intelligence. However, Goleman (1996), one of the pioneers of Emotional Intelligence, argues that cognitive intelligence alone can be insufficient for success if one does not have control and awareness of their and others' emotions. Furthermore, emotional intelligence in higher education positively contributes to mental health, learning outcomes (Ye et al., 2024), and occupational outcomes (Ahad et al., 2021).

Aim

This paper aims to explore the perceptions of CIFS students regarding the allocation of more time to the discussion of Emotional Intelligence within the current WIUT modules. It also examines students'

perceptions regarding the influence of emotional intelligence on psychological health, academic achievement, and career outcomes.

Scope

Students studying in the CIFS course at Westminster International University in Tashkent (WIUT) were surveyed and 68 responses were collected. The findings of this research can be utilized by WIUT module leaders to decide whether EI should be given greater weight and may also encourage students to engage more deeply with the concept of emotional intelligence.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Emotional Intelligence is essential for students in overcoming difficulties faced in both educational and professional settings, as well as in other areas of life, contributing to their overall well-being and personal fulfillment (Gilar-Corbí et al., 2018).

Emotional Intelligence in academic performance

Because emotional self-awareness and regulation have significant effects on individuals, there is a high correlation between Emotional Intelligence and academic performance. Emotional intelligence plays a crucial role by influencing problem-solving abilities and intrinsic motivation, allowing students to persist through challenges and achieve their educational goals (Ye et al., 2024; Moreno-Fernández et al., 2020). According to Moreno-Fernández et al. (2020), EI has a positive impact on academic performance. For example, some seminars structured to enhance Emotional Intelligence have shown improvements in overall academic achievement. These findings highlight the value of embedding EI more prominently in university curricula by developing students' emotional regulation skills. Moreover, MacCann et al. (2020) state the need for Emotional Education in universities to enhance both self-regulation and students' resilience, which are significant predictors of academic success. Thus, enhancing Emotional Intelligence through education can improve students' academic performance.

The role of Emotional Intelligence in students' well-being

Psychological well-being is one of the crucial factors of Emotional Intelligence. The correlation between psychological well-being and Emotional Intelligence is high, contributing to improved self-esteem, happiness, optimism, social encouragement and reduced depression (Chamizo-Nieto, 2021). According to Moeller, Seehuus and Peisch (2020), EI has a crucial role in students' well-being. For instance, understanding emotional intelligence helps students overcome mental health challenges and academic psychosocial pressures. Studies also indicate that knowing the role of EI can increase the psychological well-being of students (Moeller, Seehuus and Peisch, 2020; MacCann et al., 2020). Accordingly, being informed about EI helps students enrich their well-being during their academic years.

Importance of Emotional Intelligence in the Workplace

Generally, EI is positively associated with having better career outcomes. Primarily, university students will need emotional intelligence (EI) to effectively cope with professional and personal challenges when they step into the real world (Gilar-Corbí et al., 2018; Slušnienė, 2019). Additionally, EI may enhance job satisfaction by increasing positive feelings and reducing negative emotions associated with a job (Miao, Humphrey and

Qian, 2016; Kotsou et al., 2019). Ahad et al. (2021), in turn, state that positive emotions contribute to individuals being more motivated to complete their tasks. Furthermore, several studies also found a positive and significant correlation between emotional intelligence and organizational commitment, meaning people with higher emotional intelligence were less likely to leave their occupation because of potential emotional shocks of resignation (Miao, Humphrey and Qian, 2016; Ahad et al., 2021). Lastly, according to Restubog et al. (2020), emotional intelligence (EI) assists employees in effectively handling their emotions when facing chaos, uncertainties, and other work-related difficulties. Overall, EI not only increases job satisfaction and organizational commitment but also helps individuals cope with various challenges and improve their work attitudes.

Existing studies highlight the importance of emotional intelligence in academic performance, student well-being and professional environments. However, there are limited empirical studies examining the perceptions of CIFS students at WIUT regarding the significance of more hours spent on EI in current modules making this the primary focus of this study.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research participants

The participants of the research were full-time Level 3 (CIFS) students at Westminster International University in Tashkent. A total number of 68 participants recruited through convenience sampling took part in our research, making up the total number of 31 females (45.6%) and 37 males (54.4%) from the CIFS level (see Appendix 1, Figure 1). Most of the respondents' ages varied from 18 to 20 (86.8%), 8 participants were below 18 (11.8%) and a respondent was 21 or above (1.5%) (see Appendix 1, Figure 2).

Ethical considerations

Before completing the questionnaire, participants were provided with a description covering the study's purpose and ethical guidelines governing the research. Strict confidentiality was maintained throughout to protect participants' privacy, and personal or sensitive questions were excluded to minimize the risk of discomfort. Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents retained the right to withdraw at any stage without consequence.

Research instrument

To gather insights and find responses to the research question on the impact of Emotional Intelligence (EI), a quantitative questionnaire was designed to obtain students' perceptions of its role in academic success, well-being, and career readiness. A survey was selected as the primary instrument as it enables efficient data collection from a large number of participants. The survey, consisting of 13 questions, included a mix of multiple-choice, ranking, and open-ended questions, facilitating both quantitative and qualitative content analysis. The study was conducted in the form of a survey with data being gathered via Telegram CIFS chats. AI tools (Poe AI and ChatGPT) were utilized in the initial generation of survey questions and topic refinement. All AI-generated suggestions were reviewed and refined by the researchers to ensure alignment with the study's objectives and methodological standards.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section illustrates the findings of primary research. The data is based on responses from participants, specifically their views on the importance of EI in enhanced academic performance, students' well-being and preparation for the workplace. The first finding is that even though the CIFS students were taught Emotional Intelligence in the first semester, still 16 (23.5%) of the respondents did not know about EI.

Perceived Benefits of Emphasizing EI in Existing Modules

Table 1: Students' opinions for EI benefits

Benefits of more emphasis on EI	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Better stress management	51	75.0
Enhanced academic performance	33	48.5
Preparation for future career	29	42.6

The results in Table 1 show the most recognized benefits of more emphasis on Emotional Intelligence in existing modules. 75.0% (n=51) of participants selected that better stress management was

one of the key advantages, indicating that students consider EI crucial for managing stress. The second most chosen benefit was enhanced academic performance, cited by 48.5% (n=33). Lastly, 29 respondents (42.6%) reported that more emphasis on EI can help with preparation for future careers.

Impacts of EI on Academic Success and Growth

Table 2: *Impact of Emotional Intelligence in Education*

Themes	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Stress management	14	20.6
Self-awareness	9	13.2
Academic success	8	11.8
Communication skills	7	10.3
Career preparation	6	8.8
Motivation	6	8.8
Emotional Intelligence skills	5	7.4
Vague and minimal responses	13	19.1
Total	68	100%

The questionnaire results highlight students' perceptions about the integration of Emotional Intelligence (EI) into the university curriculum. The data analysis revealed that 20.6% (n=14) emphasized the benefits of emerging stress management among students, followed by self-awareness (13.2%) and academic success (11.8%). While 7 participants (10.3%) mentioned the development of communication skills, career preparation (8.8%) and motivation (8.8%) were among the most important advantages. Additionally, EI skill developments (7.4%) were also noted as valuable outcomes of the interpretation of EI in modules. However, nearly one-fifth of responses were either unclear or neutral.

Experience of academic stress

This question aimed to gather CIFS students' perceptions of how frequently they experience academic stress during their studies.

Table 3 *Academic stress among students*

How often students experience stress	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Never	2	2.9
Rarely	7	10.3
Sometimes	34	50.0
Usually	16	23.5
Always	9	13.2
Total	68	100%

According to the results shown in Table 3, 50.0% of students responded with "Sometimes," making it the most common response, while only 2.9% indicated they never experienced stress. Additionally, 13.2% of students reported always feeling stressed, and 23.5% stated they usually experience academic stress throughout their studies.

EI and well-being

This research focused on what students think can help them manage their stress and well-being.

Table 4: *Exposure to EI in students' well-being and stress management*

EI helps students to manage stress and well-being	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Yes	51	75.0
Not sure	10	14.7
No	7	10.3
Total	68	100

The findings from the quantitative analysis suggest that 75.0% of students (n=51) reported that Emotional Intelligence is important in combating academic stress. Furthermore, 14.7% of students (n=10) did not know whether Emotional Intelligence was beneficial in overcoming academic stress. Finally, 7 students considered Emotional Intelligence to be ineffective in coping with academic pressure.

EI and career success

Table 5 *The importance of EI in career success*

The importance of EI in career success	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Very Important	26	38.2
Important	25	36.8
Moderately Important	15	22.1
Slightly Important	0	0
Not Important	2	2.9
Total	68	100

Table 5 presents the respondents' views on the importance of emotional intelligence in securing workplace success. A nearly equal number of participants considered emotional intelligence to be very important (n=26, 38.2%) and important (n=25, 36.8%) for career success. Moreover, 15 respondents (22.1%) thought that the importance of EI in excelling in a profession was at a moderate level. Lastly, the data reveal that only 2 (2.9%) and no participants considered emotional intelligence to have no and slight importance for professional achievement.

EI Education for career success

Table 6 Education of EI in WIUT for greater career success

Emotional intelligence education contributes to greater career success	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Strongly disagree	3	4.4
Disagree	2	2.9
Neutral	27	39.7
Agree	24	35.3
Strongly agree	12	17.6
Total	68	100

This table examines students' views on placing greater importance on emotional intelligence (EI) to better equip them for the workplace. Notably, 27 respondents (39.7%) were neutral. Moreover, the results indicated that approximately one-third of respondents (24 respondents) wanted to have more focus on education of emotional intelligence during seminars. Half as many respondents (12 respondents, 17.6%) chose "Strongly agree", indicating a strong willingness to have more EI-centered education. Lastly, only 5 respondents did not want emotional intelligence to be more emphasized during lessons, and three of them (4.4%) expressed strong disagreement.

Overall, the statistical analysis suggests that most students see EI as a valuable tool for managing stress, improving academic and personal growth.

Discussion

Overview

The initial goal of this study was to examine first-year students' perceptions of placing greater importance on emotional intelligence education within existing WIUT modules. This section will present four principal findings, followed by a discussion of the study's limitations.

Effectiveness of EI on stress management

The results illustrate that improved stress management is perceived as the greatest benefit of dedicating more hours to emotional intelligence education. This may be because Emotional Intelligence helps individuals to identify and process their emotions more effectively, reducing the likelihood of stress escalation. These results are in line with those of a previous study by Moreno-Fernández et al. (2020), which revealed that emotional intelligence (EI) education in higher education fosters improved stress control.

Effectiveness of EI on students' well-being

Another finding that stands out from the results reported earlier is the significant role of emotional intelligence (EI) in students' psychological well-being and stress management. A possible explanation for this is that EI equips students with the ability to recognise and regulate negative emotions before they escalate into chronic stress. This, combined with the interpersonal skills that EI fosters, builds social support networks that serve as protective factors for psychological well-being. This aligns with Chamizo-Nieto (2021), who linked EI to higher self-esteem and reduced depression, and with Moeller, Seehuus and Peisch (2020), who found that EI-related skills helped students manage mental health and academic pressures more effectively.

Importance of EI for career success

The current investigation found that most of the students think that high emotional intelligence contributes to occupational success. A possible explanation is that these results are due to the role Emotional Intelligence plays in improving job satisfaction through the reduction of work-related stress. This finding was also reported by Miao, Humphrey and Qian (2016) and Kotsou et al. (2019), who found that emotional intelligence may improve job satisfaction by promoting positive affect and mitigating negative emotional experiences related to work.

Education of EI for career success

Although the majority of respondents recognized EI as professionally valuable, a considerable proportion remained neutral regarding whether dedicated teaching hours should be increased. A possible explanation is that students may feel existing modules already provide sufficient exposure to EI concepts, leading them to question whether additional curriculum time is necessary. This finding of the current study partly contradicts the previous research of Gilar-Corbí et al. (2018), where high emotional intelligence was found to be crucial in handling professional and personal challenges effectively.

Limitations of the Study

The main limitation of the study is the methodology used for the collection of data, which is a questionnaire. Students may have responded without considering all the options carefully, as evidenced by the vague responses received for open-ended questions, which further limits the depth of the qualitative findings. Furthermore, the collected data is based on students' subjective perceptions rather than measured academic outcome. Additionally, only the opinions of foundation-level students at WIUT were analyzed, which hinders the scope of the report. Moreover, the relatively small sample size may limit statistical power and generalizability of the findings. In addition to this, the use of convenience sampling limits the generalisability of findings, as participants were self-selected volunteers from a single cohort rather than a representative sample of the wider student population.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to identify the perceptions of CIFS students at WIUT about the concept of Emotional Intelligence and whether the emphasis on EI should be more integrated into current modules. According to the findings, students generally recognize the value of Emotional Intelligence in enhancing academic performance and preparing for future careers, although one in four respondents were unfamiliar with the term Emotional Intelligence. In addition, the majority of the students recognized the importance of EI in career readiness. Lastly, more than half of the participants confirmed experiencing stress during studies by acknowledging emotional intelligence as a useful tool in handling such difficulties. Overall, although there is a positive perception of EI among CIFS students at WIUT with gaps in awareness of the concept, from students' perspectives, extending the time spent on EI in the existing curriculum could benefit students both academically and professionally.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

Since 23.5% of students were unaware of the term EI, WIUT teachers should introduce dedicated introductory sessions and practical activities such as group discussions to ensure students develop a clear understanding of EI.

The Career Development Centre should organize workshops from the early years of students' academic programs, demonstrating how EI skills are applied in professional settings and helping students draw connections between their academic development and future career readiness.

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Appendices

CIFS students' perception on putting more emphasis on education Emotional Intelligence in existing modules at WIUT

Dear *CIFS students!*

The questionnaire aims to gather valuable insights of *CIFS* students regarding increasing the hours dedicated to the development of *Emotional Intelligence in existing WIUT modules*. Students with high emotional intelligence may be better able to *manage negative emotions*, such as anxiety, boredom, and disappointment that can negatively affect academic performance and future career outcomes. Collected data will be used to complete *CW2 in Academic English*.

It will take around **3-5 minutes** to complete the questionnaire, and your responses **will be kept anonymous**.

We value your honesty!

Thank you for taking the time to contribute to this research!

*Обязательный вопрос

1. What is your gender? *

- Female
- Male

2. How old are you? *

- Under 18
- 18-20
- 21-23
- Above 23

3. Do you know about emotional intelligence? (We ask you to answer honestly as * it is crucial for our research)

- Yes
 - No
-

4. What do you think would be the biggest benefit of more emphasis on EI in existing modules ? (select up to 2 answers) *

- Better stress management
- Enhanced academic performance
- Preparation for future career
- Другое: _____

5. How beneficial do you think increasing the hours dedicated to EI discussions in existing modules would be for students' academic performance? *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not beneficial	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely beneficial				

6. In your opinion, which aspects of EI are most crucial for academic success? (Select up to two) *

- Problem-solving
- Self-regulation
- Motivation
- Managing stress
- Другое: _____

7. In what ways do you think integrating Emotional Intelligence into the curriculum ^{*} could impact students' academic success and personal development?

Мой ответ _____

8. On a scale of 1–5, how important do you think Emotional Intelligence is for career success? (1- not important, 5- very important) ^{*}

1	2	3	4	5
☆	☆	☆	☆	☆

9. Which EI-related factors do you consider most valuable in the workplace? ^{*}
(Select all that apply)

- Job satisfaction
- Organizational commitment
- Problem-solving
- Regulating emotions
- Другое: _____

10. Can you share any experiences where Emotional Intelligence skills (such as self-awareness, empathy, or stress management) have helped you in academic or professional settings? ^{*}

Мой ответ _____

11. To what extent do you agree with the statement: *
"WIUT lecturers should put more emphasis on EI education in existing modules to better prepare students for the workplace".

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

12. How often do you experience academic stress? *

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

13. Do you believe Emotional Intelligence can help students manage stress and well-being? *

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

Checklist for Progress Meeting 1

#	Components	Yes	No	Comments
Research question				
	Research topic is ...	Quality Educat		
		The perception of CITS ss on		
1	identified.	✓		
2	narrowed down.	✓		
	The research question is	What are the perceptions of CITS students on the effectiveness of the training module in Wiley Cyber Center		
3	formulated.	✓		
4	focused.	✓		
5	researchable.	✓		Increasing hours dedicated to discussing emotional intelligence in existing modules?
6	feasible.	✓		
7	specific.	✓		
8	complex.	✓		
9	relevant.	✓		
Sources				
10	There are at least six sources.	✓		9 sources are use
	The sources are ...			
11	up to date (2015-2025).	✓		
12	reliable.	✓		
13	relevant.	✓		
Literature Review				
14	The literature review is complete.	✓		clear outline, Ideas should be
15	The themes are identified for the literature review.	✓		paraphrased
16	Number of themes ranges from 2-4	✓		3 themes will be discussed

17	The literature review includes paraphrases, and it includes direct quotes for purpose.		✓	no, students will paraphrase
18	There is evidence of analysis and synthesis across the studies. (This may involve comparing results and identifying differences among a number of studies)	✓		a theme-based lit. review
19	All in-text citations are incorporated appropriately.	✓		
20	The suggestions for research that needs to be conducted are mentioned (a research gap).	✓		gap is identified

Data collection method

21	The data collection method is identified.	✓		
22	Questions are formulated for the questionnaire (minimum 10 questions)/ interview (minimum 5).	✓		
23	Different types of questions are formulated for the questionnaire and/or interview.	✓		Different types of Qs are asked
24	Questions are clear and specific.	✓		
25	The (questionnaire/ interview) questions are relevant to RQ.	✓		
26	The group is ready to start the data collection process.	✓		

Student 1: 21196

[Signature]
(signature)

Student 2: 21187

[Signature]
(signature)

Student 3: 21179

[Signature]
(signature)

Lecturer: U. Abdurakhmonova

[Signature]
(signature)

*This proforma must be attached to the appendices of coursework 2

Progress Meeting 2 Proforma

Title: <i>perception of eifs students regarding increasing hours dedicated to discussing emotional intelligence in existing modules at wtu</i>		
Abstract and keywords	Yes	No
Background information is given.		✓
Purpose/s of the research study and research question are stated.		✓
A brief description of the methods is included.		✓
A summary of the main findings is given.		✓
Conclusion and recommendations are stated.		✓
Keywords are provided (5-7)		✓
1. Introduction		
Background information is given.	✓	
The rationale/reason(s) for choosing the current topic/problem (specific information) and the significance of the topic/problem are stated.	✓	
The aim(s) of the research (i.e. research question) is identified.	✓	
The scope of the study is stated.	✓	
The outline of the paper is provided (optional).	✓	
2. Literature review		
An overview of the section is provided.	✓	
Related research sources are reviewed.	✓	
Themes are identified and logically explained. They are given separately.	✓	
Ideas from sources that provide similar/conflicting/different viewpoints and/or findings are given.	✓	
In-text citations are properly incorporated.	✓	
The conclusion sums up the main ideas of the literature review and identifies the gap.	✓	
3. Methods		
Overview of the section is given.	✓	
The participants of the study (demographic data) are specified.	✓	
Ethical considerations are stated.	✓	
The description of data collection instruments is clear.	✓	
Justification for the use of data collection instruments is given. <i>(2 reasons)</i>	✓	
It is mentioned if AI tools were used and for what purposes they were used	✓	

4. Results		
Overview of the section is given.	✓	
The results of the questionnaire/interview are clearly and logically described.	✓	
Tables and/or graphs are understandable. They are appropriately/consistently labeled (in the case of the questionnaire).	✓	
Interview results are presented appropriately (summary of results, direct quotes of the interviewees, and/or block citation)	✓	
The conclusive statement(s) is provided.		✓
5. Discussion		
Overview of the section is given.		✓
The main findings are explained.	✓	
The interpretation of results is clear.		✓
Comparisons are drawn based on the reviewed literature.		✓
Limitations of the study are mentioned.		✓
6. Conclusion and Recommendations		
The aim of the study is restated.		✓
The summary of the main findings is provided.		✓
The answer to the research question is stated clearly.		✓
Recommendations specify what should be done and who can improve or solve the problem(s).		✓
7. References list		
The reference list is given.	✓	
Sources are referenced according to Westminster Harvard Referencing Style.	✓	
8. Appendices		
Appendices are organised accurately (questionnaire and/or interview questions, questionnaire results in diagrams, examples of interview transcripts, signed consent forms of interviewees, 2 progress meeting proformas).	✓	

Student 1: 000 211 96
(ID number)

(signature)

Student 2: 000 211 87
(ID number)

(signature)

Student 3: 000 211 79
(ID number)

(signature)

Lecturer:
(full name)

(signature)

*This proforma must be attached to the appendices of coursework 2